

Identity Crisis As Correlates Of Adolescents' Psycho-Social Development In Anambra State

¹Okechukwu, N. Christian & ²Prof. Nnamdi J. Obikeze

^{1&2} Department Of Educational Foundations
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study examined the identity crisis as correlates of adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State. The correlational survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study comprises 21,272 senior secondary school students in 269 public senior secondary schools in Anambra State, while purposive sample method was used to reduce the population, and got 350 as the sample size. The data was collected using a structured questionnaire structured by the researcher for the study. The data was analysed using multiple regression analysis, mean and standard deviation as a statistical technique. The study found that Self-esteem has significant influence with adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State ($F, 4.205, P, 0.003$). Personal traits has significant influence with adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State ($F, 14.29, P, 0.004$). The study recommended that adolescents' self-esteem should be enhanced by counselling psychologists by using some psychological skills and techniques. It is recommended that parents should try as much as possible to limit the extent to which their children are socially present, such as by limiting their pocket money which can be used in subscribing for data or by setting time limits on their children's gadgets.

Keywords: identity crisis, adolescents' psycho-social development, Personal traits, Self-esteem, counselling psychologists

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a very important stage of social and psychological growth and development. To reach full intellectual maturity, people go through different stages of life. Each stage is characterized by relatively similar features. Adolescence is among these stages, during which many changes occur in physical and mental characteristics of people (Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). Like other stages of life, adolescence is also associated with some crises commonly known as adolescence/identity crises. It is crucially important for adolescents to go through adolescence (identity) crisis without bearing any serious consequence. During this crisis, adolescents often seek answers to questions about their identity, and may try different ways to finally find their true identity. One of the main concerns of adolescents is to establish their true identity (Chen, Bao & Gao 2021).

Self-esteem is one of the factors considered in this study as factors that could influence the identity crisis of in-school adolescents, can be referred to one's feeling of worth and it can also be described as one's personal evaluation of worth. Harter (2019) opined that self-esteem as the evaluative and affective dimension of the self-concept is considered as equivalent to self-regard, self-estimation and self-worth. It is also seen as in-school adolescents' general appraisal of their high or low value based on their ratings of different roles and domains of life (Markus, 2023). Self-esteem is seen as the sum of one's beliefs and knowledge about one's personal attributes and qualities. It is classed as a cognitive schema that organises abstract and concrete views about the self, and controls the processing of self-relevant information

(Markus, 2019, Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024). Other concepts, such as self-image and self-perception, are equivalents to self-concept.

Self-esteem is the evaluative and affective dimension of the self-concept, and is considered as equivalent to self-regard, self-estimation and self-worth (Harter, 2019). It refers to a person's global appraisal of his/her positive or negative value, based on the scores a person gives him/herself in different roles and domains of life (Rich et al 2020), 2016). Self-esteem is generally defined as how the individuals feel about themselves, and it is an important psychological variable because it affects many parts of one's life (Kernis, 2023). Positive self-esteem is not only seen as a basic feature of health and wellness, but also as a protective factor that contributes to better health and positive social behaviour through its role as a buffer against the impact of negative influences. It is seen to actively promote healthy functioning as reflected in life aspects such as achievements, success, satisfaction, and the ability to cope with psychological and health-related issues.

Conversely, an unstable self-esteem and/or poor self-esteem can play a critical role in the development of an array of disorders and social problems, such as depression, anorexia nervosa, bulimia, anxiety, violence, substance abuse and high-risk behaviours. These conditions not only result in a high degree of personal suffering, but also impose a considerable burden on society. It has been demonstrated (Bayraktar, Sayil & Kumru, 2019, Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). that individuals with low self-esteem show higher externalising problems such as delinquency, antisocial problems and aggression. Rosenberg (1965) reported that individuals with low self-esteem have weak relations with society, and this gives rise to more delinquency and aggression. Individuals with low self-esteem are generally unhappy and dissatisfied with themselves (Kernis, 2023) and this could result in an identity crisis.

Personality is another identified factor that could influence identity crisis among adolescents, and this refers to those set of qualities of an individual that helps him understand, analyse, interpret and act or react to a person, situation or environment. Personality dimensions are those characteristics that account for consistent patterns of behaviour (Suchita & Vaishali, 2023, Ohanyere, Arinze, & Atueyi 2025). Personality traits reflect people's characteristic patterns of thoughts, feelings, and behaviours. Personality traits imply consistency and stability, and one who scores high on a specific trait like Extraversion is expected to be sociable in different situations and over time. Thus, trait psychology rests on the idea that people differ from one another in terms of where they stand on a set of basic trait dimensions that persist over time and across situations. The most widely used system of traits is called the Five-Factor Model (Cheng and Furnham, 2022). This system includes five broad traits that can be remembered with the acronym OCEAN: Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism. Each of the major traits from the Big Five can be divided into facets to give a more fine-grained analysis of someone's personality (Cheng & Furnham, 2022).

It has been observed that personality is a significant predictor of mental health, including positive mental health/wellbeing (Cloninger & Zohar, 2021). Healthy personality development is related to several aspects of emotional and behavioural-related issues and there is a need for integrating the contributions of personality to behavioural issues on current approaches to mental health (Cloninger, 2022, Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025). Studies using personality models derived from linear factor analyses, such as the Five-Factor Model (FFM) (Gutiérrez et al., 2019), found negative associations between Neuroticism and happiness and psychological related issues (Garcia, 2021), positive associations between neuroticism and negative effect, between openness and positive affect and between conscientiousness and life satisfaction and adolescent (Garcia, 2021). Thus, this study examines on adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to ascertain the relationship between identity crisis and adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State. Specially, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between self-esteem and adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State.

2. Find the relationship between personal traits and adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Identity Crisis

Sokolowski of the Merriam Webster Dictionary (2018) defined identity crisis as a personal psychosocial conflict especially in adolescence that involves confusion about one's social role and often a sense of loss of continuity to one's personality. Angus of the Oxford Living Dictionaries (2018), defines identity crisis as a period of uncertainty and confusion in which a person's sense of identity becomes insecure, typically due to a change in their expected aims or role in society. According to the Collins English Dictionary (2018), identity crisis is a state in which a person experiences uncertainty about who they really are and their proper role in life. Erikson coined the term identity crisis, to describe the uncertainty, and even anxiety, that adolescents may feel as they recognize that they are no longer children and become puzzled and confused about their present and future roles in life.

Over the years, researchers have developed elaborate interviews, questioning adolescents and young adults to determine if interviewees have experienced a crisis (grappled with identity issues) and whether or not they have made commitments (that is, resolved any issues raised) with respect to forging occupational, interpersonal, political, religious, and sexual identities. Based on the answers provided, the interviewee is classified into one of four identity statuses for each identity domain. A strong identity emerges not only from a conscious contemplation of your life's purpose, but also from successfully resolving the developmental challenges that characterise the previous childhood years. Having a strong sense of trust in infancy, autonomy in toddlerhood, ability to play at preschooler years, and solid work ethic in the elementary school years (Whitbourne, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Identity Statuses Theory of Marcia

Similarly, to Erikson, Marcia (1993) sees the identity crisis as beginning when adolescents recognize the need to establish an identity that can prepare them to meet the challenges of adulthood. For true identity achievement adolescents need to explore the many possibilities in lifestyles, roles and career choices. Individuals can detect identity achievement when individuals gain a clear understanding of their own strengths and weaknesses and a clear set of personal standards. In Marcia's theory exploration and commitment are the main dimensions determining the status of identity. According to his investigation there are four identities resulting from the combinations of low and high values of the dimensions.

Real identity achievement is based on meeting the challenge (exploration) and making the commitment. There are some who try to avoid the crisis, some try to avoid the commitment, and some try to avoid both. If either the challenge or commitment is avoided, role confusion takes place. Identity diffusion is the first status, when adolescents avoid the challenge and refuse to make a commitment. The danger of this status is that diffused individuals are weak in self-management and handling negative influence. The second status is foreclosure, when the individual avoids challenge by making a commitment without any exploration. This happens often when individuals try to serve the plans and goals of their parents and not their own ones. The third status is moratorium, when the individual consolidates exploration and challenge without making a commitment. The fourth status is identity achievement. It means that the individual makes commitments after collecting experience and testing challenges. These four identity statuses (Identity diffusion, Identity foreclosure, Moratorium, Identity achievement) describe phases along a continuum moving from an initially diffuse, undefined individual identity to a highly specific, individual sense of self.

In Marcia's theory is the assumption that a mature and well-adjusted person possesses a well-defined and specific identity. This assumption reflects an implicit set of values common to many developed societies; but, this set of values may not be universally shared. In contemporary Western cultures great value is placed upon individual needs, rights, and freedoms. Therefore, it can be understood why such societies define maturity in terms of a highly evolved sense of an individual self. But in other cultures, the needs of the larger community are more important than any single individual's. In such cultures, maturity is

defined by the ability to subjugate individual pursuits and desires in the service of the group's greater good.

Review of Empirical Studies

Margret, et al. (2022) investigated the effects of self-esteem and development of ego-identity on innovative work behaviour among in-school adolescents. In their study, the researchers examined the effects of self-esteem and development of ego-identity on innovative work behaviour among in-school adolescents in Enugu State. Four research questions guided the study and four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Ex-post facto or causal comparative research design was adopted. The population includes the 1972 senior secondary 11 in-school adolescents in the Nsukka education zone. Three instruments used in the study include: Adolescents Ego-identity Questionnaire (AEIQ) and Innovative Work Behaviour Questionnaire (IWBQ). A reliability coefficient of 0.87 for ASEQ, 0.83 for AEIDQ, and 0.91 for IWBQ respectively was an indication that the instruments were reliable enough to be used for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the four research questions, whereas independent t-test and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used in testing the four hypotheses. The results of the findings among others show that self-esteem, gender and location has effect on and respectively influence the development of ego-identity of in-school adolescents in Nsukka education zone. The study also revealed that innovative work behaviour moderated in-school adolescents' self-esteem and ego-identity. Based on the findings, the study recommended among other things that government, school administrators, parents and other stakeholders should take note of the influence of gender, location and innovative work behaviour in influencing self-esteem and ego-identity of in-school adolescents.

The reviewed study is related to the present study in that it both studies examine self-esteem among in-school adolescent which is the main thrust of the present study. The two studies differ in geographical scope. The current study was carried out in Anambra state, while the reviewed study was in Enugu State. The reviewed study's case of study development of ego-identity on innovative work behaviour, why the current study case study was on psycho-social development.

Saputra, Muji & Palupi, Listyati. (2020). examined personal identity processes and self-esteem: temporal sequences in high school and college students. They examined how identity processes were associated with self-esteem in high school and college students. Cross-lagged analyses in three longitudinal studies found that commitment making and identification with commitment were positively related and ruminative exploration was negatively related to self-esteem. A self-esteem main-effects model was supported in high school students (with self-esteem predicting these identity processes) and a reciprocal model was supported in college students (with identification with commitment and ruminative exploration being reciprocally related to self-esteem). Apparently, high self-esteem functions as a resource for tackling identity-related issues such as identity crisis in high school and college students. When adolescents enter college and make the transition to adulthood, identity consolidation, in turn, increasingly plays into self-esteem as well.

The reviewed study differs from the present study in that it both studies examine personal identity processes and self-esteem: temporal sequences in high school and college students. The two studies differ in geographical scope. The current study was carried out in Anambra state, while the reviewed study was in China.

Yagana & Alhaji (2019). examined the effect of identity development, self-esteem, low self-control and gender on aggression in adolescence and emerging adulthood. He reported that the identity crisis seems to be an extensive and serious problem among adolescents and emerging adults, with negative adverse effects. In his study, he aimed to examine the relations between identity dimensions (formation and crisis), low self-control, self-esteem, gender and life period (adolescence and emerging adulthood) with aggression. A structural equation model was developed and tested. In this model, the dependent variable was identity crisis and formation while the independent variables were demographic variables (gender and life period), identity dimensions, self-esteem and low self-control. Participants consisted of 240 adolescents (high school students 132 female and 108 male) and 244 emerging adults (university students-128 female and 116 male) and their age was between 15-24 years old (mean age=18.99,

SD=2.62). The Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire, The Dimensions of Identity Development Scale, The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, and The Low Self-Control Scale were used to collect data. Findings of his study showed that life period, exploration in depth, ruminative exploration, self-esteem and low self-control significantly predicted identity formation and crisis. According to model analysis, 100 the best predictor of identity crisis was low self-control; the weakest predictor of identity crisis was low self-control.

The reviewed study is related to the present study in that it both studies examine of identity development, self-esteem which is the main thrust of the present study. The two studies differ in geographical scope. The current study was carried out in Anambra state, while the reviewed study was in Instabul.

Suchita and Vaishali (2022) investigated the impact of personality dimensions on identity crisis among adolescents. They explored the relationship between personality dimensions and identity crisis of adolescents if any. In their study, standardised tests were administered to obtain the scores on self-image of students (considered as the indicator of identity crisis) and scores on different dimensions of personality. Based on the results of the study, it was observed that personality dimensions of adolescents do not play any significant role in causing identity crises among adolescents. Adolescents are able to cope well with their situations and people around them and live rather comfortably. The study indicates that personality dimensions do not become causal factors for identity crises.

The reviewed study is related to the present study in that it both studies examine of identity crisis among adolescents which is the main thrust of the present study. The two studies differ in geographical scope. The current study was carried out in Anambra state, while the reviewed study was in Indonesia.

Eliseo (2019) examined the association between personality dimensions (extraversion and emotional stability) and identity crisis. A total of 368 students from the University of Rovira i Virgili completed the Extraversion and Emotional stability subscales of the revised Eysenck Personality Questionnaire, identity crisis Scale, and the Positive and Negative Affect Scale. Regression analyses revealed the personality variable of emotional stability as one of the most important correlates of identity crisis as it has negative correlation with identity crisis. Regression analyses also showed that 44% of the variance of identity crisis was accounted for by emotional stability, whereas extraversion only explained 8% of the variance.

The reviewed study is related to the present study in that it both studies examine of personality dimensions and identity crisis. which is the main thrust of the present study. The two studies differ in geographical scope. The current study was carried out in Anambra state, while the reviewed study was in Rovira.

A study of Lu and Shih (2019) found that extraversion retained its direct (and the strongest) effects of happiness or identity crisis, whereas the effects of emotional stability were largely mediated by mental health. According to the literature about the correlation between extraversion, emotional stability, and identity crisis, extraversion appears to be the most important predictor of identity crisis among selected adolescents.

Sanju, et al. (2019) investigated the relationship between emotional stability and identity crisis of rural students in Sabah, Malaysia. This was a cross-sectional study of 430 students and they found that 73% of students rated their emotional stability as moderate and 90% rated their identity crisis as moderate. Regression analysis showed that emotional stability could predict identity crisis. Findings of our study are useful to policy makers if they want to improve the mental health and identity crisis of adolescents. There is a need for psychoeducational intervention in schools to raise awareness about the impact of personality on identity crisis and to minimize the impact of it on identity crisis among secondary school students.

The reviewed study is differs from the present study in that it studied emotional stability and identity crisis of rural students in Sabah, Malaysia. The two studies differ in geographical scope. The current study was carried out in Anambra state, while the reviewed study was in Malaysia.

METHOD

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive research design. Nworgu (2015) defined co-relational design as a type of research that tries to determine the relationship between two or more variables.. The rationale for adopting this design is to determine the extent to which identity crisis relates with adolescent's psycho-social development in study area.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises 21,272 senior secondary school students in the 269 public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. Senior secondary school students is made up of 9550 males and 11722 females from the 269 public senior secondary schools in Anambra state. The information was gathered from the post primary school service commission, Awka 2025. The decision to use this population is because the researcher noticed the high commitment of parents and teachers in education of their children and high rate of juvenile delinquency activities going on in the area.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size for the study will consist of 350 SS2 students in Anambra State. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw 172 students from Onitsha North LGA, 178 students from Anambra state, making a total of 350 students who participated in the study. the samling techniques used was simple random sampling

Instrument for Data Collection

Three instruments was used for data collection, the researcher structured questionnaire titled effect of identity crisis on adolescent's psycho-social development (ICAPD) in Senoir secondary schools in Anambra State. The respondents respond to the instrument using the following codes

Strongly Agree SD (4)

Agreed A (3)

Disagreed D (2)

Strongly disagree SD (1)

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected for the study was analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. All data collected was analysed using SPSS Version 26.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter dealt with presentation, analysis of results and summary of major findings.

Presentation and Analysis of Results

The results were presented in the tables with analysis according to research questions.

Research Question 1; *What is the relationship between self-esteem and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Mean rating of the self-esteem and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	SD	D	SVD	MEAN	REMARK
1	On the whole, I am satisfied with myself	190	126	15	16	2.44	3.71	Accepted
2	At times I think I am no good at all	218	99	15	15	1.55	3.66	Accepted
3	I feel that I have a number of good qualities	270	50	10	17	1.48	3.85	Accepted
4	I am able to do things as well as most other people	234	58	26	29	2.75	3.07	Accepted
5	I feel I do not have much to be proud of	269	50	15	13	2.14	4.72	Accepted
6	I certainly feel useless at times	227	89	13	18	1.83	4.85	Accepted
7	I feel that I'm a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others	264	58	11	14	1.94	4.60	Accepted
8	I wish I could have more respect for myself	148	170	14	15	2.48	3.65	Accepted

Table 1 revealed that there is relationship between self-esteem and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State, as the cumulative response mean of 2.6 was less than the decision mean of 3.6. The implication of this result is that, self-esteem helps adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State. Also, the respondents agree strongly with all the ten items tested on this research question has the high response mean.

Table 2: What is the relationship between personal traits and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State?

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	SD	D	SVD	MEAN	REMARK
1	I see myself as someone who is reserved	64	142	55	86	1.62	3.89	Accepted
2	I see myself as someone who is generally trusting	165	150	15	17	1.89	3.44	Accepted
3	I see myself as someone who tends to be lazy	217	93	14	23	1.50	4.60	Accepted
4	I see myself as someone who is relaxed, handles stress well	270	50	10	17	1.204	4.45	Accepted
5	I see myself as someone who has few artistic interest	234	58	26	29	1.120	3.18	Accepted
6	I see myself as someone who is outgoing, sociable	269	50	15	13	1.60	3.58	Accepted
7	I see myself as someone who tends to find fault with others	227	89	13	18	1.71	3.17	Accepted
8	I see myself as someone who does a thorough job	217	93	14	23	1.62	3.21	Accepted
9	I see myself as someone who gets nervous easily	148	170	14	15	1.224	3.74	Accepted
10	I see myself as someone who has an active imagination	213	93	25	16	1.75	3.89	Accepted
Cumulative Mean		= 3.4						

Table 2 revealed that there is relationship between personal traits and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State, as the cumulative response mean of 2.6 was less than the decision mean of 3.4. The implication of this result is that, personal traits helps adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State. Also, the respondents agree strongly with all the ten items tested on this research question has the high response mean

4.4 Hypotheses Testing

The five null hypotheses formulated for this study were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis One: Self-esteem does not relate with adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Statistics on the mean ratings of self-esteem and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State

Status	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-critical	Prob.
Between Groups	.295	2	.295	4.205	3.15	.003
Within Groups	866.278	345	1.650			
Total	866.573	347				

Table 3 showed the f-ratio value of (4.205) at 2 df 557 and at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The critical value (3.15) is less than f-ratio value (4.205), the probability level of significance P(.003) is less than 0.05. This means that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of self-esteem and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypotheses accepted which implies that Self-esteem relate with adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two: Personal traits does not relate with adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Statistics on the mean ratings of personal traits and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State

Status	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-critical	Prob.
Between Groups	1.330	2	1.330	14.29	3.15	.004
Within Groups	678.446	345	1.292			
Total	679.776	347				

Table 4 showed the f-ratio value of (14.29) at 2 df 557 and at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The critical value (3.15) is less than f-ratio value (14.29), the probability level of significance P(.004) is less than 0.05. This means that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of personal traits and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

In conclusion, the issue of identity crisis plays a critical role in shaping the psycho-social development of adolescents in Anambra State. Adolescence is a transitional stage marked by the search for self-definition, belonging, and independence, and when young people are confronted with identity confusion, it often influences their emotional stability, social interactions, academic performance, and future aspirations. In Anambra State, where cultural traditions, family expectations, religious values, and the pressures of modernization intersect, adolescents often face conflicting influences that either support or challenge their ability to achieve a stable sense of self. Those who successfully navigate identity challenges are more likely to demonstrate higher self-esteem, resilience, confidence, and positive social relationships, while unresolved crises may result in deviant behavior, peer pressure susceptibility, substance abuse, and poor adjustment in society.

The psycho-social development of adolescents in the state is therefore not only a personal or family concern but also a community and societal responsibility. Parents, teachers, religious leaders, and policymakers play vital roles in providing guidance, mentorship, and supportive environments that foster healthy identity formation. Schools should integrate life-skill education, counseling services, and moral instruction to help students cope with developmental challenges. Similarly, cultural and community-based initiatives that respect traditional values while embracing positive aspects of modernity can contribute to a balanced identity formation process.

Ultimately, addressing identity crisis among adolescents in Anambra State is fundamental for building a generation that is emotionally stable, socially responsible, and capable of contributing meaningfully to societal growth. When adolescents are supported to develop a coherent sense of identity, they are better equipped to handle life's challenges, maintain healthy relationships, and make responsible decisions that strengthen not only their personal lives but also the broader socio-economic and cultural fabric of the state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made

Evolving from the results and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations have been put forward;

- i. It is recommended that adolescents' self-esteem should be enhanced by counselling psychologists by using some psychological skills and techniques. The findings of the study have proven that personality negatively correlates with identity crisis and adolescents. Thus,
- ii. it is recommended that personality of adolescents can be adjusted by counselling psychologists through the use of some psychological therapy programmes such as schema-focused therapy and cognitive behavioural therapy which will help to reframe disruptive behaviour to positive and healthier personality.

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